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***Concept of God and religious involvement of adults in Kerala:
What it is and why it is.***

Abstract

The concept of God has an age-old history. It has changed through the times and has had different peculiarities / interpretation in different civilizations. Research has shown that the image or concept of God as possessed by different individuals can affect their thought processes and social interactions. In the same way, it can be assumed that involvement within a religious community can also be influential on how an individual thinks and acts in society, which in turn influences how a society functions and stays together as a group. The present study was intended to understand the concept of God among believers in Kerala who belong to three major religions: Hinduism, Islam, and Christianity. The study also explored the subjects' involvement in religious communities and why they do so. There were 60 participants, and a semi-structured interview was conducted. Thematic and percentage analyses were done to analyse the data. The major concepts regarding God are the controller, creator, invisible power, protector, judge, etc. And involvement in a religious community is found to be related to social conformation and obedience.

Keywords: Concept of God, Religious Involvement, Adults, Kerala

Introduction

God has an age-old history with the existence of human life. There are different religions and spiritual systems that hold different views of God regarding his physical and existential qualities. In religious texts and discussions by different theologians and philosophers, the concept of God holds different explanations. In India, among different religious believers, when considering the number of believers, Hindu, Muslim, and Christian, 80.5 percent, 13.4 percent, and 02.3 percent, respectively, are in the first three places. All three religions have prescribed religious texts and stories that narrate about God. When we go through Hindu 'Puranas' (writings in Hindu mythology), we will come to encounter Gods with endless power and the ability to give powers to others through "Vara" (blessing of God in Hindu mythology). In Hindu 'puranas' there are Gods with human nature and structure like 'Rama' and 'Krishna' and without any sort of physical structure like 'para Brahma', the ultimate power. There are

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male and female Gods in Hindu 'Puras' and '*Shiva-Shakti*' is the concept that represents the balance of nature. A single religion holds this much difference in concepts about Gods and different '*Pandithas*' (people who possess religious knowledge) give different explanations of God in the Hindu religion itself. There is also an argument that Hinduism cannot be said to be a religion because it is a combination of different cultural streams in India with different traditions, rituals, ways to worship Gods, and ways of life. In this particular study, people who reported their religion as Hindu were included).

Islam is based on the concept of a single ultimate power that has no form, sound, smell, or taste. It is a gender-free concept, even if people mention it as "he." In Islam, "*Allah*" is the one and only God who is believed to have created and maintained the world and is eternal. "He" is the one who deserves all worship, and man was created to worship 'Him'. People who follow him are asked to worship Him, without questioning, and he will nurture them even after death. According to the Quran, "He is the God; there is no God other than Him. He is the lord of mercy, the controller, the holy one, the source of peace, the granter of security, and the guardian overall. " He is the almighty, the wise."²

Christianity also holds a single God concept. According to the Bible, believers are instructed to love God "with all their hearts, with all their souls, and with all their strength."³ The Bible says God is all-powerful, all-knowing, and eternal. We cannot see or touch God, but we can see that he does wonders in the world and that he is loving, compassionate, merciful, patient, and forgiving. They believe that we can communicate with God through prayer, and he will judge all of us after death.

Philosophers and psychologists have also tried to explain the concept of God in different ways. In philosophy, there have been discussions about God for a long time. In the ancient period, Aristotle talked about God. Aristotle ultimately argues that there must be a God, in the form of an unmoved mover, who is responsible for the reality of the world. The discussion continued through the medieval period, and modern thinkers like Descartes and Spinoza also put forward different arguments about the concept of God. For example, Descartes writes that "By the word God I mean a substance that is infinite, eternal, immutable, independent, supremely intelligent, supremely powerful, and which created both myself and everything else (if anything else there is) that exists."⁴ In contemporary philosophy, we can also see philosophers like Heidegger and Sartre who are interested in exploring these ideas.

The conceptualization of an individual's image of God has been in the theoretical interest of psychology at least since Freud introduced it as a psychological construct.⁵ Recent developments in the psychology of religion focus on the development of God's image in individual minds and its impacts on individual behaviour and social interaction. According to leading ideas, God serves as an attachment figure or a transitory object within the human mind.⁶ Cognitive research shows that when highly religious participants talk to God through prayers, brain areas usually used for social interaction are working, which means that the participant is interacting with God as he interacts with other people.⁷ Developmental psychology studies have revealed that young children initially think of God as having a person-like understanding.⁸ By the time they reach the age of five, children begin to differentiate God, to whom they attribute extraordinary knowledge, from ordinary people.⁹ Also, studies show that initially held theological beliefs about God do not supersede earlier ones but rather coexist with them.¹⁰

Hall and Annie Fujikawa talked about implicit (a representation of God based on the sentiments and experiences of the individual) and explicit (a conception of God that is propositional and based on people's conscious judgments and claims). They also argued that social contact at the organizational and societal levels has an impact on and is impacted by one's perception of God. This is especially important for people who live in religious communities because religious beliefs are at the heart of congregational life in those groups.¹¹

Research shown below also indicates that the image of God has a significant influence on a person's response to God and also on a person's worldview and interaction with their surroundings. God's image is an interactive product that has an impact on a person's social life. As an interactive product, God Image can affect a person's social life. Anger towards God results from a cruel image of God (because they believe that God deliberately causes some negative event).¹² or fear of God (many believe that God is all-powerful and actively intervenes in the world)¹³ If people believe that God is harsh, then we anticipated that they would express more worry over God's disapproval.¹⁴

Adherence to a wrathful and judgmental God image leads the person to perceive the world in narrow categories of good and evil,¹⁵ This perspective is linked to a rigorous devotion to biblical authority in civic concerns,¹⁶ possessing a less-forgiving moral stance, and lower levels of social trust.¹⁷ Individuals who have a more forgiving and sympathetic view of God are less likely to rely on religious texts and tradition; instead, they make moral decisions using personal

reason and pragmatism.¹⁸ The image of God as benevolent and loving is positively correlated with support for social and economic justice,¹⁹ and people who believe in a personal God (seeing the connection between oneself and loving God) yield emotional benefits, whereas the authoritarian image is correlated with a wish for more merger of the state and the church and believe that God takes a side in world affairs.²⁰ The image of God as one who takes an active interest in human affairs (active representation) is also positively correlated with a conservative political attitude.²¹ Differences in the image of God are also found to influence a person's religious commitment²² and volunteering.²³ The present study is intended to explore the concept of God among people of different religions and the beliefs and practices related to these beliefs. In Kerala, according to the census of 2011, among the population, 54.73 percent are Hindus, 26.56 percent are Muslims, and 18.38 percent are Christians. Sikh and Buddhist Jain religious believers constitute 0.01 percent each, 0.02 percent of the population belong to other religions, and 0.26 percent are stated as having no religion. From the data, it is clear that the major religions in Kerala are Hinduism, Islam, and Christianity.

According to the economic survey for 2021–2022, Kerala is in the first position in literacy rate and school education quality, only 4 cases were charged in 2020 under communal/religious riots.²⁴ At the same time, the devotee nature of Kerala can be seen in the number of religious institutions, the people who regularly go to them, and in social responses related to issues like women's entry in Sabarimala (a temple in Kerala where women's entry had certain restrictions). The researcher is interested in knowing about the image of God in this Keralite community as a beginner so that its impact on the reaction to religious issues in Keralite society can be studied later. Knowing about this will also be helpful to understand how the concept of God is working in an educated group of people who reside in a nation where multiple religions exist and secularism is fundamental as suggested by the constitution. The researcher here considers the God concepts of individuals belonging to these three religions, irrespective of the God concepts described in religious texts.

It is crucial to take into account a person's participation in their religious group as a pertinent facet of their beliefs. Involvement in the religious community through norms and rituals can influence a person's social actions. According to research by Robert Putnam and David Campbell (2012), having friends who practice the same religion as you can also inspire you to get involved in your community²⁵. Religious community members who have strong social relationships with one another allow the group to have a greater influence over the actions of

its members, and those who have these ties are more likely to readily adhere to its standards, share its ideals, and engage in its sanctioned activities²⁶. In the present study, the researcher is also interested in studying the involvement of subjects in the religious community, which can also be helpful in further investigations.

Objectives

1. To explore the concept of God among adults in Kerala
2. To explore the involvement with the religious community among the adults of Kerala

Method

Participants - The participants were 60 adults from different districts of Kerala, of which 44 belong to the Hindu religion, 10 belong to the Islamic religion, and 6 follow the Christianity religion.

Procedure

After extensive reading and discussion semi-structured interview schedule was prepared which included open-ended questions related to God's image, participation in religious rituals, obeying religious customs, etc. Consultation with an expert was done to validate the interview schedule. After fixing the appointment, participants were individually met, the researcher talked to them about the purpose of the interview, and consent was taken. Each interview took almost 30 to 45 minutes including the rapport establishment. After interviewing 5 participants, necessary changes were made in the interview schedule so that maximum information can be elicited and make the question appropriate and understandable to the participants.

Results and Discussion

God has been a matter of discussion in psychology for years. Researches show that the individual concept of God can be influential in an individual's social and religious behaviour. The present study investigates the concepts of God among adults in Kerala and is interested to find out how far they are involved in their religion and religious belief through direct interviews.

Among the respondents, 41 percent had completed higher education, 33.33 percent completed graduation, and only 11.6 percent quit formal education below the 12th level. Almost all the subjects were believers in God, but only 4 percent reported that they do not believe in the existence of God in any manner. Among people who believe in the existence of God, their concept of God and the reason behind their belief vary among the respondents.

In the major theme concept of God, the investigator found different sub-themes. The sub-themes include: God is the controller (God controls everything; birth, death, life events, etc. are decided by him; we can't make any change in our lives if God didn't intend to, etc.); creator (He created us; He is the father of all of us); invisible power (it is a power that we can trust in hard times; it gives us power and strength to fight; it is a force out there); omnipresent (He is the one who presents everywhere; He is there in every living and non-living being; He is the life inside us; He is present in every moment and witnesses everything, so we can't cheat Him); omnipotent (He can do everything; nothing is impossible to Him, so believe). if we truly believe in Him, He will do anything for us; He will do miracles if we don't doubt Him), single force (He is only one and He protects us all; only one God is there; all other powerful Gods are the parts or forms of Him). multiple forces (there are different Gods and people will have "*Istadaivangal*" (one or more favourite Gods of a person whom he/she prays and admires more), there are Gods for special wishes and there is time for special wishes, sometimes if we don't give proper rituals, the God will face "*Shakthikhaya*", which means a particular God, in particular, a place will lose His power). Protector (He protects us from every harm; if we believe in Him, He will be there to protect us in hard times). He judges our actions and thoughts, and He will treat us according to that. He will give us an afterlife according to our actions in the world. He notices and gives a mark to everything we do, good and bad. He will judge our actions and decide for us according to our karma. Always dependable (we can trust and depend only on Him, even when no one is with us; He will never leave our hands; there are times when anything on earth can help us, but we can depend on Him, and He will). Previous research shows that having a judgmental and punitive God-image can lead to a more punitive attitude toward social and moral issues.²⁷ In the data, we can see people who hold this sort of concept of God. Even if the concepts include dependability, protection, etc., the explanation always stresses the need to pray and trust God to achieve this. Sub-themes, including dependents and protectors, show the concept of God as an attachment figure.

Participants also reported that they believe in God because, "He created us," "everyone believes in God so that must be true," "if we ignore God he will punish us," "because He is the ultimate truth and He nurtures and protects us," "He will listen to us if we believe and He has powers that can make everything possible," "He gives us the courage and when doing activities related to a belief like a payer can feel happy and if we are true to our prayer God will fulfil our wish," "because He is the only one we can ultimately depend on or He is the only one we have because we have a lot of experiences that prove that there is God".

While looking into the responses and considering the themes that emerged about the concept of God, it can be assumed that the kind of concept of God and reasoning for belief people hold depends on the hope and courage it can give them. Most of the time, it is related to fears, and participants need to have a protective figure in these fears. The fears can be real or imaginary; they can be associated with the present or future; they can be triggered from inside or outside; they can be associated with actions of God or actions of self and other beings. The data also suggest that subjects lean towards God when uncertainty appears. When they are insufficient to meet the demands of a particular situation, they look up to God because their concepts of God suggest that he can do anything. Every concept God emerged from the data is useful to give courage and hope in the face of fear. Strong negative concepts are less prevalent in the participants, but we can see the fear of punishment and gratitude for happiness that they achieve from their beliefs. The responses also show that the participants hold on to God as something that can be trusted. The concepts of participants show a similarity of concepts of God because there are religious texts, especially in Semitic religions, that show the influence of religious learning in creating the concept of God.

The study's secondary goal was to explore the involvement of adults in religious communities in Kerala. This objective was added to have a preliminary understanding of the religious participation of people in Kerala and to understand the motivation behind this participation. The result is shown as a bar diagram below.

Of the believers, 90 percent of them are living according to the religious standers and are performing religious rituals and activities, and the level of this performance has variation in regularity and intensity among the performers. 48 percent of subjects believe in the existence of heaven and hell. When looking into the performance of religious activity during major life events like birth and new beginnings in life like marriage and death, 96 percent of the subjects are performing religious rituals (all of the subjects who reported that they believe in God are

performing religious rituals, even though 6 percent among them claim that they are not living exactly according to the religious standards of behaviour).

66 percent of subjects consider “*Vasthu Vidhya*” (traditional Indian rules of architecture) while constructing a new home (86.36 percent of Hindus and 20 percent of Muslims), and 96 percent of subjects do one or another sort of religious behaviour in the housewarming (all Christian and Muslim subjects perform religious behaviours, while 95.45 percent of Hindu subjects do it). 73 percent of the respondents believe in astrology (88 percent are Hindu, 33 percent are Christians, and 30 percent are Muslims). 50 percent of them believe that religious education is important (all Islam and Christian subjects believe, while 31.8 percent are Hindus), and 41 percent are regular readers of religious texts (96 percent of Christians and 98 percent of Muslims, while 20 percent of Hindus). 80 percent believe in offerings (every Christian subject, 60 percent of Muslims, and 81 percent of Hindus), and 11 percent believe in divine healing (9 percent of Hindus, 20 percent of Muslims, and 16 percent of Christians).

People who believe in the existence of heaven and hell justify their beliefs based on religious texts. They said that "there is a detailed description of this in the religious texts, and that must be true" and "we can see how correctly religious texts describe the existing world and the changes in the world, so if that is correct then the notion about hell and heaven also must be correct". This can be explained by the need for cognitive simplicity, and previous research shows that believers are highly in need of cognitive simplicity.²⁸ Some of them described it based on a lack of other knowledge; they say that "until now, science has not been able to create life or give a satisfactory description of what happens after death, but religion explains it, and there is no evidence available for its nonexistence. so that must be some truth", another category of responses includes "God is *Neethiman*" (which means God is righteous), so after death, there should be something that gives benefits for good deeds and punishment for bad things people have done, so there must be hell and heaven". We can see a human tendency to answer a question about death using logic and imagination. The belief in hell and heaven may be relieving the anxiety of death; it may satisfy the need for meaning in life and the need for justice because heaven and hell give the ultimate hope for justice. While going through the responses, we can see how participants are trying to hold on to something that gives answers to unanswered questions about human life, even if they don't have any proof of that.

Response categories of People who perform religious activity on major life events include "*Nattunatapp*" (the unwritten rule about how people should behave in a certain situation in a

particular village or a particular community); they say that "it is how the major life events like birth, marriage, death, etc. are addressed within their community and religion". They say that "they never thought about why it is relevant; they know that it is relevant because that is the way others in their group behave". Another category of responses includes "all are performing this, and each ritual and behaviour related to these activities has its meaning and results, which is why for years and years people have been doing these behaviours in a certain manner". The next category of responses is like "Even if we know there is nothing important in these rituals and it is a waste of money, we can't stay in peace without doing that; if we don't, it will affect our status in society, and most of the time, all family members and relatives will pressure us to behave in a certain manner and perform all the rituals related to the events; we can't escape from that". Yet another category of responses includes "we are supposed to do so because religion says to do so; if we don't perform, it will be "*Kuttam*" (sin) according to the religion" and a further category includes "it is good to perform such activities; it will increase our acceptance in eternal life". The last category responses were like "It will increase the social connection and interaction; it will help to meet all family members; and doing such rituals and celebrations together will increase the love and connectedness among the family members". The responses show that religious rituals are followed for mainly three reasons: conformity to social rules; obedience and fear elicited from religion; and a social and emotional benefit gained through rituals. Human beings are social animals, and the culture and connectedness in society have a huge impact on them. Even in this postmodern era, results show that involvement in religious rituals gives acceptance in society, and avoiding them leads to negative experiences in society.

People who believe in "*Vasthu Vidhya*" and astrology have given an almost similar explanation for their behaviour. In the case of "*Vasthu Vidhya*" response categories include "it is a science that is based on some mathematical calculation related to the geographical placement of the spot and the relation of it with the universe", "it is created through continued inquiry, and it is there in books, so that is true". Another category of responses includes an explanation of their own experience, others' experience, or stories of experience that are shared by others, which include bad experiences related to "*Vasthu Dosha*" (problems in life that happen due to not following the traditional architecture called *Vasthu Vidhya*) and how the change in construction related to "*Vasthu Vidhya*" changed their lives.

The next category of responses includes. It gives you an assurance of safety, and you can work and live in peace". And a further category expressed fear about what would happen if something wrong happened if we ignored it and said that "if something went wrong, then everyone would blame the person who ignored the *Vasthu Vidhya*".

The same responses were received about astrology. Categories of responses include "their thrust is based on experiences or shared stories of experiences", "people didn't believe in it for a long time if it was not true", "it is a science based on some mathematical calculation" and "it helps us gain control over future happenings, which we can't do in any other manner". "It gives some solution or acts when we have no idea what to do to overcome certain difficult situations". The last category includes "explaining events happening in our lives that we can't understand in any other manner".

In both cases, responses show fear of harm and uncertainty. As human beings don't know about the future, this sort of belief gives them some assurance about their safety in the future. The tendency to believe in stories can also be seen in these responses.

Response categories of people who argue for religious education include "religious knowledge is the primary knowledge, and all other knowledge is irrelevant without religious knowledge." "Religious education is essential for your entire life and to live a proper and good life" and "all other knowledge will end in this small, unreal life, but religious knowledge will be the only knowledge that will help you in your real life after death". Another category of response includes "lack of religious knowledge will destroy your community, and through that, you will get destroyed" and "lack of religious knowledge keeps you away from your group".

The last category includes responses like "religious communities with more religious knowledge will have more unity and will be able to destroy religious communities with a lack of religious knowledge". Categories of responses from people who read religious texts regularly include a notion of ultimate knowledge; another category includes "it is a regular practice in the family and it was learned in childhood", "it is good for the home and family and it brings prosperity to the family", "it gives peace and fullness to the mind and becomes disturbed if skipped reading" and "it is mandatory in religion and if read properly and regularly you will get the benefit of that in your afterlife". The responses show that even if science and modern education have developed so much, common people still give importance to religious education and believe that it is important. It may be because religious texts give definite

answers to existential questions, and they may be useful in fulfilling cognitive needs. Religious education may be helping them to bond as a community that shares common knowledge about the world and the truth. This may be helpful to fulfil the need for belongingness.

Reasons people believe in offerings fall into categories like "based on their own or others' experiences or based on stories they have heard." They include stories or experiences related to the fruitfulness of their wishes, tragedies that happened after forgetting or degrading offerings, and dream experiences or predictions by astrologists related to offerings. Another category of responses says "this will give you peace and confidence", and "what else is there to do in complicated situations that we can't handle by our self". Responses of people who believe in divine healing fall into the categories "God created disease, and he will be able to cure it," and "without belief in God, no medicine will be able to help". No subject is entirely dependent on divine healing. People who trust in divine healing believe that things like offerings, black magic, etc. will help cure a disease that medical science is not able to cure. This response also shows people's tendency to trust superstitions to solve problems, and sometimes they even feel that they are getting results from their beliefs. The responses show that offerings help them to be at peace when life is uncertain, and this peace of mind may be reinforcing their behaviour to again make offerings. Stories from others can also act as a reinforce of the behaviour.

Conclusion

The present study intended to understand the concept of the God of people in Kerala. The major concept relates to God in Kerala society includes controller, creator, invisible power, protector, judge, and dependable entity. The concepts are related to fear, the need for protection, and hope for justice. The study indicates that even though Kerala is a well-educated state with a good standard of life people still need belief in God to feel secure. In the case of involvement in religious rituals, social conformity and religious obedience, and peace of mind are reported as the reasons to involve in it. Further inquiries need to be done to understand the social and personal consequences related to the concepts of God and the reasons for involvement in religious rituals.

Notes

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